

Flipkart Customers’ Satisfaction of Online Shopping with Reference to Bengaluru City

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Dr. HK. Prasad

Associate Professor, Jain College- CPGS, Bangalore

AV. Akshay Kumar

Assistant Professor, Jain College- CGS, Bangalore

Abstract

Online shopping or e-shopping is a method of electronic commerce which permits consumers to directly purchase goods and services from a seller through internet using web browsers. The development of online shopping has opened door of chance to offer a competitive advantage over firms. Online shopping has developed in popularity over many years mainly because people discover it convenient for the comfort of their home and workplace. Thus, the study aims to look at the buyer satisfaction towards on-line purchasing from flipkart. The study emphasizes on online shopper’s preferences, customer satisfaction and their problems on Flipkart online shopping marketers. The study is grounded on both primary and secondary data. Likert’s five point scale and Convenient Sampling technique were utilized in this study for choosing the samples and also the sample size for the study was seventy. With a view of examining the data through percentage analysis. Research findings from the paper will be beneficial to understand the customers’ level of satisfaction on basis of the product further as websites practiced by many shoppers.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, online buyers, online shopping.

Introduction

Internet is changing the way consumers shop and buy products and services and has rapidly progressed into a global phenomenon. Several companies have started using the Internet with the purpose of cutting costs related to marketing, thereby decreasing the price of their products and services in order to stay ahead in the competitive markets. Companies also practice the Internet to convey, communicate and broadcast information, to sell the merchandise, to require feedback and additionally to conduct satisfaction surveys with customers. So many customers practice the Internet not only to buy the product online, but also to check and compare prices, product features and post-sale service facilities they will receive if they purchase the product from a particular retail store. Many people are optimistic about the prospect of online business.

In addition to the potential of the E-commerce market, the Internet affords exceptional chances for companies to more efficiently reach existing and potential customers.

Through e-marketing and web communication Business Company’s selling place measure coordinating completely different promoting activities like market research, development, inform customers concerning product options, promotion, client services, and client feedback then on.

Online shopping is used as an intermediate for communication and electronic commerce, it is to increase or improve in value, quality and appeal of delivering customer benefits and better satisfaction, that is why on-line looking is additional convenience and day by day increasing its quality. Not only benefits but also risk is related with online shopping.

Generally speaking net users avert on-line looking as a result of credit card fraud, lack of privacy, non-delivery risk, lack of guarantee of quality of products and services. Specific authorities are production policies to minimise the chance concerned obstacles in e-business. In Liao and Cheung (2000) words:” Fraud-free electronic shopping” was introduced by uk of Britain and Northern Ireland within the early 1995 and once 2 years Europe and Singapore hosted secured electronic dealings (SET).

On alternative the opposite facet E-commerce has been grown-up in no time as a result of various blessings related to shopping for on net as a result of lower dealings and search price as compared to other types of shopping. With the help of online shopping consumers can buy faster, more alternatives and can order product and services with comparative price.

Online shopping permits the consumers to directly buy goods from the seller through internet. It is also known as web-store, e-shop or online store. Online customers should have access to the web to shop for product kind on-line. People can gaze at these websites of online stores and purchase products in comfort form home. Till now the consumers were majorly visiting online to reserve hotel rooms, buy air, rail or movie tickets for buying books and electronic gadgets, but now many offline products like cloths for all segments, beauty cosmetics, electronic accessories, shoes and consumer durables are now being purchased online.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is that the live of however the requirements and responses area unit collaborated and delivered to stand out client expectation. It will solely be earned if the client has Associate in Nursing overall sensible relationship with the provider.

In today’s business marketplace, customer satisfaction is a significant performance exponent and basic differentiator of business strategies. A lot of is buyer satisfaction; a lot of is that the business opportunities and also the attachment with many shoppers.

Customer satisfaction could be a part of customer’s expertise that exposures a supplier’s behavior on customer’s expectation. It conjointly depends on however expeditiously it’s managed and the way promptly services area unit delivered. The buyer satisfaction may be related to numerous business aspects like product promoting, product producing, engineering, quality of product and services, responses customer’s issues and queries, completion of project, post delivery services, grievance management etc. buyer satisfaction is that the essence of the impression concerning the supplier by the purchasers. This impression that a client makes relating to provider is that the assemblage of all the method he goes through, right from communicating supplier before doing any marketing to post-delivery choices and services and managing queries or complaints post-delivery.

Through this process the customer comes across working environment of various sections and the type of strategies involved in the organization. This supports the customer to make strong opinion about the supplier which finally results in satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Review of the Study

The work of Kim and Park (2006) using U.S. samples proposes that their positive attitudes and willingness to search for pre-purchase information hints to a strong likelihood that they will

buy online. Online shoppers are mandatory to have computer skills in order to use the Internet for shopping. Hence, people are not comfortable with using the computers, will likely do their shopping at the traditional store, modern shop, or discount store (Monsuwe, 2004) because it will be faster shopping there than in the Internet shopping.

Home catalogue is another best traditional selling channel where people can shop at home because of the diversities of products offered in the catalogue. They can order by the phone or by mail. It's so convenient except that they're unable to touch and feel product before getting Sultan and Henrichs (2001) in their analysis terminated that the consumer's disposition to and preference for adopting the net as his or her looking intermediate was conjointly absolutely associated with financial gain, house size, and originality. Vijay, Sai. T. & Balaji, M. S. (May 2010), revealed that Consumers, all over the world, are increasingly fluctuating from the crowded stores to the one-click online shopping format. Anyhow, irrespective of the convenience offered, online shopping is far from being the most preferred form of shopping in India. A survey among more than 150 internet users, including both internet users and non-users of online shopping, was carried out to understand why some purchase online while others do not.

Rashant Singh (2014), in his study on Consumer's shopping for Behaviour Towards on-line searching, the most aim of study was to look at and analyse the consumer's shopping for behavior pattern towards on-line searching in Bengaluru. The analysis is looking on each primary knowledge and secondary knowledge. The entire sample sizes of forty were collected through form by exploitation convenient sampling technique, the end result of the study is most range of users is incredibly happy on on-line searching and primarily fascinated by shopping for on-line apparels.

Need for the Study

Marketing is mainly focusing on the consumer's needs more effectively and efficiently with the great products and services with the better price, product shopping access and deliver. A marketer constantly adjusts to change and to satisfying his consumers need in a better way. Sometimes chance to address the consumers in better way is designed by marketers himself and occasionally it is offered by the technology. Internet is changing the way consumers shop for products and services and has rapidly evolved into a global result. People are getting busy with their work. In their busy schedule they don't find free time for shopping. Online shopping can protect a lot of time for them. They can do this from their office or home by browsing on the internet this paper is to analyse who the consumers are much satisfied out of the online services.

Objective of the Study

1. To evaluate the satisfaction level of the online buyers on the basis of product & web characteristics.

2. To identify the respondents or customers perception about online shopping.
3. To analyse the possible factors those affect the buying from online shopping portal-flipkart.

Statement of the Problem

To enrich and charm on-line client it is very much necessary to perceive regarding their shopping for behavior and understand what they really need. Since on-line looking methodology is that the new medium of looking with new demands of individuals. All customers have their own needs and demands and expectations for product in order that it's terribly crucial for all on-line retailers to spot and understand their on-line customers.

Significance of the Study

The present study is mainly concentrating on the buying awareness, satisfaction level of buyers and problems faced by of respondents. Hence the results of the study will surely be useful to the customers who prefer online shopping.

Scope of the Study

The significance of the study is to understand regarding the shopping for behavior of consumers on on-line looking portals. It's been known in educational analysis and its literature, but during this particular gap persists broader and to some extent fragmented. Therefore, the aim of the study is to check the customer's awareness level and shopping for angle towards on-line product and services.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is that the specific procedures or techniques able determine, select, process, and analyze the data a couple of explicit topic. During this analysis paper, the methodology section permits the reader to judgmentally analyse a study's overall validity and dependability.

Methodology

A. Collecting the data/ information

The present study is primarily supported the perceptions, and buying behavior and satisfaction of the purchasers in Indian market. Sources of the first and secondary information are mentioned. The interview technique is employed for the aim of gathering primary information or data. The study is conducted in Bengaluru town by taking seventy respondents mistreatment convenient sampling technique. The secondary information is collected kind the many websites, completely different national and international journals is employed associated with the sector of management similarly as selling business magazines.

B. Questionnaire

To evaluate the satisfaction of the purchasers mistreatment on-line looking Likert's five category scale is employed with scales goes as “Highly positive, positive, neutral, negative and extremely negative”. so as to gather the info concerning products' options and web site options the scientist has used a four purpose Likert Scale

C. Sample Size

Convenient Sampling technique was utilized in the study for choosing the samples and therefore the sample size for the study was seventy.

D. Statistical Tools

The following tools utilized in the study:

Simple percentage analysis

Percentage of Respondents= Number of Respondents $\times$ 100 Total Respondents

Limitations of the Study

However it is an in depth analysis, it is not free from the limitations. The following are the limitations of this study:

1. The sample size was limited to 70
2. Lack of time for research study

Analysis and Interpretation

Researcher has done the analysis on the following:

1. Assessment of customer’s opinions on on-line product options.
2. Assessment of customer’s understandings on internet service and provided options.

A. Percentage Analysis of Socio-Economic Details of Respondents

The demographic factors of the respondents’ like Gender, Age, academic Qualification, and Occupation are taken for analysis and simple average technique has been adopted.

Table 1
A. Demographic Variables of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Age	20-30	39	56
	31-40	21	30
	41-50	10	14
Gender	Male	37	53
	Female	33	47
Education	Undergraduate	41	58.5
	Postgraduate	19	27
	Others	12	17
Occupation	Employed	18	26
	Business	15	21
	Students	30	43
	Other	7	10
Income	Below 1 lacks	8	11
	1-2 lacks	38	54
	2-3 lacks	9	13
	Above 3 lacks	15	21.4
Website you prefer	Flipkart	31	44.2
	Amazon	23	33
	Myntra	11	15.7
	Others	5	7.1

Table-1 Interpretation

The above table demonstrates that the highest number of respondents 56% belongs to 20-30 years age group and 30% belongs to 31-40 years age group, while 14 % respondents belongs to 41-50 years age group .The table shows that 53% are male respondent while 47% are female respondent. The study reveals that 58.5% respondents were undergraduate, while 27% are post graduate. Occupation of the respondents is important socio economic variables which decide social, cultural, economic status of one’s. The table indicate that 26% respondents were employed, 21% respondents are from business class and remaining 30% are students. The above data also reveals that 44.2% respondent is flipkart users for online shopping.

Table 2
Assessment of Customer’s View on Product and Website Features

Product Features	Highly Satisfied		Satisfied		Neutral		Dissatisfied		Highly Dissatisfied	
	Count	Mean	Count	Mean	Count	Mean	Count	Mean	Count	Mean
Quality goods are available	22	-31.4	39	-55.7			9	-12.8		
On time delivery	30	-43	38	-54.2	2 (3)					
Online shopping is more convenience	11	-16	43	-61.4	13	-19	2	-3		
Time saving/ convenience	20	-28.5	28	-40	19	-27	3	-4.2		
Purchase return is possible	3 (4.2)	41	-58.5	10	-14	12	-17	4 (5.7)		
2. Web Feature/ service	Highly Satisfied		Satisfied		Neutral		Dissatisfied		Highly Dissatisfied	
Wide variety of brand choice are available on website	31	-44.2	27	-38.5	12	-17				
Goods are delivered on time	24	-34.2	25	-36	15	-21	6	-8.5		
Goods are delivered with good condition	11	-16	36	-51.4			21	-30	2 (3)	

Latest Product Information is available on website	35	-50	33	-47.1		2	-3			
Payment method is so easy	26	-27	31	-44.2	1 (1.4)				12 (17.1)	
Payment security			37	-51			15	-21	18 (27)	
After sale service	3 (4.2)	20	-28.5	11	-16	36		-51.4		

B. Assessment of Customer’s View on Product and Website Features

Table: 2 Interpretations

The on top of table we analyse that majority of respondents selected on-line buying satisfaction for quality product on the market (36%), purchase come (58.5%), on time delivery (54.2), whereas the remaining respondents are glad for product delivered on time (36%), respondents are glad for the products delivered with shape (51.4%) ,respondents are extremely glad for up to date product info is accessible on web site (50%).The respondent shows discontent solely once the sale service (51.4%).

Findings

1. Majority of respondents are glad by smart quality merchandise are on the market, with timely delivery, glad by purchase come policy and additionally payment security of flipkart.
2. Majority of respondent are extremely glad as latest product info is accessible to them, sort of complete selection is additionally on the market within the web site of flipkart.
3. Some respondent feels that once sale service aren’t up to the mark in flipkart

Suggestions

1. The online shopping deficiencies in after sales service that leads to less number of online shopping customers.
2. The products that require after sales service should aim the facility to attract more number of online customers
3. Consumers should be educated on online shopping procedures with proper steps to be followed while purchasing through online.
4. Company should provide their payment security for the customers

Conclusion

The online shopping develops a daily part of our lives as it is more convenient, consumers are looking for timely services, better quality of products, customer services and also security and privacy in payment method. The study reveals that most of the undergraduate students belongs to age (20-30) years are more aware about shopping from flipkart. This research study concludes that the online shopping from flipkart is best one among all. The study about the various aspects of customer’s satisfied from online shopping through flipkart portal.

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